
Unveiling Gamma Ray Burst Afterglows Through Multiwavelength Spectral Modeling: An Application to GRB 221009A

DESY Summer Student Programme, 2023

David Raudales

National Autonomous University of Honduras, Honduras

Chengchao Yuan

Marc Klinger

Theoretical Astroparticle Physics (THAT)

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Theoretical Tools	2
2.1	Synchrotron Radiation	2
2.2	Synchrotron Self-Compton	3
3	Numerical Spectral Energy Distribution Modelling	3
3.1	Steady State Solutions	4
3.2	Combined Coolings	5
3.3	Steady State SSC Model	6
4	One Zone SSC Model of GRB 221009A	8
5	Conclusions	9
6	Acknowledgements	9

1 Introduction

Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs) are intense, short-lived outbursts with tremendous energies released in gamma-ray bands, which makes them unrivaled laboratories for high-energy astrophysics. The radiative output of GRBs is a two-act scenario: the prompt emission, characterized by an intense burst of hard X-rays/soft-gamma-rays within the initial seconds, and the subsequent afterglow, an enduring glow observed across the electromagnetic spectrum that can persist from days to months. GRBs are categorized into two primary classes: long-duration bursts, believed to originate from massive star core collapses, and short-duration bursts, typically associated with the merger of compact objects like neutron stars. In either case, such an event leaves behind an engine for relativistic jets. The prompt emission is typically explained by internal energy dissipations, while the afterglow is related to emission from an external shock resulting from ejecta-medium interactions [19].

The contrast between the prompt emission's complex temporal features and the smooth evolution of the afterglow, makes the latter a great laboratory for the processes governing particle acceleration. It is this afterglow that constitutes the focal point of our investigation. Typically, the description of a GRB afterglow aligns with the idea that the non-thermal radiation, spanning from radio frequencies to soft-gamma-rays, emerges primarily from leptonic synchrotron emission. Meanwhile, the most energetic gamma-rays are attributed to inverse Compton scattering, where synchrotron photons are elevated in energy through interactions with their parent electron population.

GRB 221009A, the brightest GRB detected to this date, was first detected by the GRB Monitor (GBM) and Large Area Telescope (LAT) on the Fermi Spacecraft ([18],[1]). 53 min later, the Burst Alert Telescope (BAT) on the Swift spacecraft detected the burst. Observations were then taken with Swift's X-Ray Telescope (XRT) 143 later [7]. Shortly after, the Monitor of All-sky X-ray Image (MAXI) reported the detection of a bright X-ray emission from the same location[13]. The Neutron Star Interior Composition Explorer (NICER) also contributed with X-ray detections [11]. Ground based observatories also took place in the observations. The Large High Altitude Air Shower Observatory (LHAASO) gave us puzzling information about the Very High Energy [(VHE) > 100 GeV] gamma rays. LHAASO's Water Cherenkov Detector Array detected 64,000 photons within 3 ks [4]. GRB221009A was observed by LHAASO for around 4 ks.

As part of DESY's summer program, we have undertaken the development of a one-zone, time-dependent Synchrotron Self-Compton (SSC) model to elucidate the afterglow emission of the aforementioned GRB.

In the following sections, we will provide a concise overview of the pertinent radiation processes and subsequently delve into the mathematical equations essential for conducting numerical simulations of these radiation processes within our spectra. Our objective is to contrast the outcomes of our simulated SSC model with theoretical expectations. Ultimately, we will present a spectral model for GRB221009A's afterglow at different times, which incorporates the concept of a blast wave as the radiation zone. Our analysis will explore the dynamics of this system and its photon emission, all while drawing comparisons to observed data.

2 Theoretical Tools

2.1 Synchrotron Radiation

The emission of non-thermal radiation by relativistic particles interacting with a magnetic field is believed to be the responsible mechanism of GRB afterglows [17]. It is commonly assumed that electron acceleration predominantly occurs within a relativistic shock wave that propagates through the surrounding circumburst medium [2], details can be found in further sections. In the comoving frame of the fluid the emitted synchrotron power (dE/dt) by a single relativistic electron is given by

$$P(\gamma_e) = \frac{4}{3} \sigma_T c \gamma_e^2 U_B \quad (1)$$

where $U_B = B^2/8\pi$ is the magnetic field energy density. The synchrotron radiation by an electron translates in energy losses during a timescale estimated as its energy over the emitted power, i.e.,

$$\tau_{syn}(\gamma_e) = \frac{\gamma_e m_e c^2}{\frac{4}{3} \gamma_e^2 \sigma_T c U_B} = \frac{9}{8\pi} \frac{h}{\alpha} \left(\frac{B_c}{B} \right)^2 \frac{m_e c^2}{\gamma_e} \quad (2)$$

where the critical magnetic field $B_c = m_e^2 c^3 / \hbar e = 4.4 \times 10^{13}$ G is used. Note that for a given dynamical time t_{dyn} , electrons with an energy higher than a critical Lorentz factor, aka cooling Lorentz factor

$$\gamma_c = \frac{9}{8\pi} \frac{h}{\alpha} \left(\frac{B_c}{B} \right)^2 \frac{m_e c^2}{t_{dyn}} \quad (3)$$

lose a significant fraction of their energy due to radiation. Throughout the text we will assume that the injected particle energy distribution follows a power law as predicted for a shock acceleration mechanism. Therefore, the electron energy distribution is characterized by

$$n_e(\gamma_e) d\gamma_e = A \gamma_e^{-p} d\gamma_e, \quad \gamma_{e,m} < \gamma_e < \gamma_{e,M} \quad (4)$$

where A is a normalization constant and the total number of electrons is $N_e = \int dV \int d\gamma_e n_e(\gamma_e)$. $\gamma_{e,m}$ and $\gamma_{e,M}$ represent the minimum and maximum Lorentz factors respectively.

The spectral power, $P_\nu = dE/d\nu dt$, achieves its maximum value at a characteristic synchrotron frequency estimated as [17]

$$\nu_f(\gamma_e) = \frac{B}{B_c} \frac{m_e c^2}{h} \gamma_e^2. \quad (5)$$

An expression for the pitch-angle-averaged synchrotron spectral power can be found in [6]. In order to obtain the net spectrum for a given particle distribution, the synchrotron spectral power of individual particles is integrated with the corresponding particle distribution over the possible energies. The number flux is then

$$F_\nu \propto \int_{\gamma_{e,m}}^{\gamma_{e,M}} P_\nu(\gamma_e) n_e(\gamma_e) d\gamma_e. \quad (6)$$

It is now necessary to contemplate two different cases. In the case that $\gamma_{e,m} < \gamma_c$, not all of the electrons are able to cool. In this *slow cooling regime* the flux results to be

$$F_\nu \propto \begin{cases} (\nu/\nu_m)^{1/3} & \nu_m > \nu \\ (\nu/\nu_m)^{-(p-1)/2} & \nu_c > \nu > \nu_m \\ (\nu_c/\nu_m)^{-(p-1)/2} (\nu/\nu_c)^{-p/2} & \nu > \nu_c \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $\nu_m = \nu_f(\gamma_{e,m})$, $\nu_c = \nu_f(\gamma_c)$ and $\nu = \nu_f(\gamma_e)$.

Conversely, when $\gamma_{e,m} > \gamma_c$ all the electrons cool within a cooling timescale, e.g., Eq 3, which is shorter than the dynamic timescale. Now electrons are in the *fast cooling regime* and the flux becomes

$$F_\nu \propto \begin{cases} (\nu/\nu_c)^{1/3} & \nu_c > \nu \\ (\nu/\nu_c)^{-1/2} & \nu_m > \nu > \nu_c \\ (\nu_m/\nu_c)^{-1/2} (\nu/\nu_c)^{-p/2} & \nu > \nu_m \end{cases}. \quad (8)$$

2.2 Synchrotron Self-Compton

The inverse-Compton (IC) scattering of seed photons within the emission region, elevating them to higher energies, also stands as a significant radiation mechanism in the context of GRB afterglows. Notably, when these seed photons originate from synchrotron radiation produced by the same electron population, the process is identified as *Synchrotron Self-Compton* (SSC). In the rest frame of the electron, if the energy of the incident photon is significantly lower than the electron's rest energy, the IC is said to be in the *Thomson regime*. Otherwise, the IC is in the *Klein-Nishina regime*, where the electron recoil plays an important role and the inverse Compton emission is suppressed in the high-energy end. The following discussion will focus on the Thomson regime, for a more elaborated discussion see [3] and [8].

The IC emission power of a single electron takes the form

$$P_{IC}(\gamma_e) = \frac{4}{3} \sigma_T c \gamma_e^2 U_{ph} \quad (9)$$

with U_{ph} being the energy density of the target photons. In the SSC model $U_{ph} = U_{syn}$ and it is convenient to define the parameter

$$Y = \frac{P_{SSC}}{P_{syn}} \approx \frac{U_{syn}}{U_B}. \quad (10)$$

With this definition the IC cooling timescale becomes

$$\tau_{IC}(\gamma_e) = \tau_{syn}(\gamma_e) \frac{1}{Y}. \quad (11)$$

In general, the SSC photons can be scattered again leading to a second-order SSC component. Higher order SSC components are also possible. This means that one can define

$$Y_1 = Y = \frac{P_{SSC,1}}{P_{syn}} \approx \frac{U_{syn}}{U_B} \quad (12)$$

$$Y_2 = \frac{P_{SSC,2}}{P_{SSC,1}} \approx \frac{U_{SSC,1}}{U_{syn}} \quad (13)$$

and so on. The total emission power is then

$$P_{total} = P_{syn} + P_{SSC,1} + P_{SSC,2} + \dots \quad (14)$$

or in terms of the Y parameter,

$$P_{total} = P_{syn}(1 + Y_1 + Y_1 Y_2 + \dots). \quad (15)$$

Usually for GRBs higher order SSC components are subdominant meaning that

$$P_{tot} = P_{syn}(1 + Y) \quad (16)$$

The IC flux is given by [16]

$$F_\nu^{IC} = R \sigma_T \int_{\gamma_{e,m}}^{\infty} d\gamma_e n_e(\gamma_e) \int_0^{x_0} dx F_\nu(x) \quad (17)$$

where R_{co} is the size of the emission region, F_ν is the synchrotron flux. Moreover, for an incident photon with frequency ν_0 being scatter to an energy ν_1 the parameter x is defined as

$$x = \frac{\nu_1}{4\gamma_e \nu_0}. \quad (18)$$

The value $x_0 \sim 0.5$ ensures energy conservation[16]. For a power law distribution of electrons, the IC spectrum follows the same shape of its parent synchrotron spectrum, see Eqs. 8 and 7. On the other hand, the IC characteristic frequencies can be estimated as $\nu_m^{IC} = 4\gamma_e \nu_m x_0$, $\nu_c^{IC} = 4\gamma_e \nu_c x_0$.

3 Numerical Spectral Energy Distribution Modelling

The time-dependent simulation of particle spectra depends on the interplay between different processes. While new particles are being injected, old particles

cool and escape the system. Therefore, the energy distribution of these particles can be described by a set of coupled integro-differential equations

$$\frac{\partial n_i(E, t)}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial E} \left[\frac{E}{\tau_{cool}} n_i(E, t) \right] - \frac{n_i(E, t)}{\tau_{esc}} + Q_i(E, t) \quad (19)$$

where i denotes different particles. The first and second terms on the RHS account for particle cooling and escape respectively. The last term, $Q_i(E, t)$, is a source term that represents generation and injection rate of particles. In this work, the calculation of diverse spectra was performed using the Astrophysical Multi-Messenger Modeling (AM³) code [12] [9]. Additionally, all quantities were calculated in the comoving frame of the fluid.

3.1 Steady State Solutions

As an astrophysical system evolves, particle injection can be matched by escape and cooling. This implies $\partial_t n_i = 0$, meaning that a *steady state* in which the particle distribution stops evolving is reached. In order to understand the behavior of the differential equation, we solved it through AM³ for a couple of interesting cases.

Dominant Escape. As a toy model, let's consider a spherical emitting region with a continuous injection of electrons obeying a power law. We will assume that the rate at which particles escape is significantly faster than the rate at which they cool, making the cooling term in Eq. 19 negligible. At the steady state, the solution to Eq. 19 is

$$n_e(E) = Q_e(E)\tau_{esc}. \quad (20)$$

Since electrons move at relativistic velocities, the escape time can be estimated as $\tau_{esc} = R_{co}/c$, neglecting any spatial diffusion and adiabatic cooling. Eq. 20 means that after the necessary time steps, the electron distribution has to converge to a factor of the original injected electron spectra, this can be seen in Fig. 1 where a spectral index of $p = 2$ was considered.

Figure 1. Time evolution of the computed electron spectrum for a escape dominated spherical system.

The general time dependent solution can be obtained by solving

$$\frac{\partial n_e}{\partial t} = -\frac{n_e}{\tau_{esc}} + Q_e(E) \quad (21)$$

leading to

$$n_e(E, t) = Q_e(E)\tau_{esc}(1 - e^{-t/\tau_{esc}}) \quad (22)$$

Fig. 2 shows that the time needed for the system to reach the steady state is approximately $4\tau_{esc}$, telling us that a couple of dynamical times are enough. The system was evolved by simulating timesteps of, $dt = 0.01\tau_{esc}$.

Figure 2. Distribution of electrons as a function of t/τ_{esc} for an electron energy of $E = 1$ GeV.

Dominant Adiabatic Cooling. If coupled, particles confined in an expanding region will undergo energy losses as they do work. The energy losses of particles are related to the expansion rate of the region. In the following, we considered this *adiabatic cooling* to be constant with energy. Additionally, a negligible escape timescale is assumed. For a steady state, Eq. 19 then reduces to,

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial E} \left[\frac{E}{\tau_{adi}} n_e \right] + Q_e(E) = 0 \quad (23)$$

Note that there are now two cases to consider:

1. $E_m \leq E$. For this case Eq. 23 leads to

$$E n_e(E) = \tau \int_{E_m}^E Q_e(E') dE' \quad (24)$$

assuming $Q_e(E) = A E^{-2} e^{-E/E_M}$ and noting that

$$\int k E^{-2} e^{-E/E_{max}} dE = -k \frac{e^{-E/E_{max}}}{E} - \frac{k E_i(-E/E_{max})}{E_{max}} + C \quad (25)$$

we finally get the desired solution

$$n_e(E) = \tau_{adi} Q_e(E) \times \left(1 + \frac{E}{E_{max}} E_i(-E/E_{max}) e^{E/E_{max}} \right) \quad (26)$$

where $E_i(x)$ is the exponential integral function.

2. $E_m > E$. In this regime there is no injection which leaves us with

$$E n_e(E) = C \quad (27)$$

It is possible to find the constant C by continuity,

$$n_e(E) = \frac{E_m}{E} n_e(E_m) \quad (28)$$

Fig. 3 shows the analytical solution, electron injection and simulations for different integer multiples of the adiabatic cooling timescale. A cooling tail is produced under the minimum electron energy due to adiabatic cooling. As expected from Eq. 28, this cooling tail has a spectral index of 1. Additionally, a little attenuation is caused at high energies for the same reason.

Figure 3. Time evolution of the electron distribution for an adiabatic cooling dominated system. Analytical solution according to Eqs. 28 and 26 is shown.

Dominant Synchrotron Cooling. Synchrotron cooling, as previously discussed, is of great importance in the modelling of GRB afterglows. Commonly, it is the main cooling to which charge particles are subject to. For practical reasons let's rewrite the energy dependent timescale, Eq. 2, as $\tau_{syn}(E) = \beta E^{-1}$. The transport equation is then given by

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial E} \left[\frac{E^2}{\beta} n_e \right] + Q_e(E) = 0 \quad (29)$$

Now the energy loss rate is proportional to E^2 . The equation above can be solved analogous to Eq. 23. Below the minimum energy, the solution becomes

$$n_e(E) = \frac{E_m^2 n_e(E_m)}{E^2} \quad (30)$$

Above the minimum energy, we obtain the same form as before but with the energy dependent synchrotron

cooling timescale

$$n_e(E) = \tau_{syn}(E) Q_e(E) \times \left(1 + \frac{E}{E_{max}} E_i(-E/E_{max}) e^{E/E_{max}} \right) \quad (31)$$

The SED for different timescales compared to the analytical solution is shown.

Figure 4. Time evolution of the electron distribution for a synchrotron cooling dominated system. Analytical solution according to Eqs. 30 and 31 is shown

3.2 Combined Coolings

Once with accurate simulations for synchrotron and adiabatic losses we can simulate a steady state where both cooling mechanisms take place. In cases where more than one cooling timescale relevantly influences the system dynamics, the cooling term in Eq. 19 is estimated by considering the combined effect of both synchrotron and adiabatic cooling, as expressed in $\tau_{cool}^{-1} = \tau_{syn}^{-1} + \tau_{adi}^{-1}$. The electron and photon energy distributions were computed for this scenario, as depicted in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. Of particular interest is the exploration of how the particle spectrum responds to variations in a key parameter, namely the intensity of the magnetic field. This parameter holds exceptional significance due to its influence on the synchrotron cooling timescale. From a value of $B = 0.1\text{mG}$ we increased the magnetic field by an order of magnitude four times. The system was evolved for around 10 adiabatic timescales, ultimately reaching a steady state in every case. For the electron injection, the minimum electron energy is set to $E_m = 1\text{GeV}$, while a maximum electron energy of $E_M = 1\text{PeV}$ is imposed.

Figure 5. Steady state electron spectrum for variations of the magnetic field. Vertical lines correspond to the energy at which synchrotron cooling overcomes adiabatic cooling.

Figure 6. Synchrotron spectra resulting from the electron spectra shown in Fig. 5. Same color code is preserved. Vertical lines obtained with the characteristic energies related to vertical lines shown in Fig. 5.

The electron spectrum shows breaks around the maximum and minimum injection energies as expected. Additional breaks are explained by the change on the dominant cooling timescale. This can be estimated by equating the synchrotron and adiabatic timescales, resulting in cooling break energies of

$$E_{e,co} = \frac{9}{8\pi} \frac{h}{\alpha} \left(\frac{B_c}{B} \right)^2 \frac{1}{\tau_{adi}} \quad (32)$$

As appreciable from Fig. 7, for a magnetic field of $B = 1\text{G}$ (blue line) the synchrotron cooling timescale is significantly faster than the adiabatic timescale starting from energies as low as around 1MeV . Therefore, the electron spectrum has the same shape as in Fig. 4. It is worth mentioning that since $\gamma_c < \gamma_{e,m}$, we are in the fast cooling regime. A slow cooling regime counterpart can be seen for the case of $B = 0.1\text{mG}$ (cyan line), where the adiabatic timescale mainly dominates.

Note that the cyan line follows the shape of Fig. 3. For the case of $B = 10\text{mG}$ (green line), on one hand, the adiabatic cooling dominates before the break energy and the spectrum resembles the expected shape. On the other hand, after the break the spectrum resembles the shape of a synchrotron cooling dominated spectrum.

Figure 7. Timescales plot from Fig. 5

3.3 Steady State SSC Model

A comparison between our simulations for a SSC model and analytical expectations for both a slow cooling and a fast cooling scenario are shown, see Figs. 8 and 11. Here, the electron distribution is assumed to have a spectral index of $p = 2.5$. Moreover, electrons are accelerated with an acceleration timescale estimated as [10]

$$\tau_{acc}(E_e) = \eta \frac{E_e}{eBC} \quad (33)$$

where η is an efficiency factor. Since for our simulations the inverse Compton cooling is never dominant over synchrotron, equating the acceleration timescale (Eq. 33) to the synchrotron timescale (Eq. 2) allows us to estimate the maximum energy reached by electrons

$$E_{e,M} = \sqrt{\frac{\eta 6\pi e}{\sigma_T B}} m_e c^2. \quad (34)$$

For a better visualization interaction rates are presented in Figs. 10 and 13.

The analytical model was treated following what is presented in Sec. 2. We can see that the analytical cooling breaks are consistent with our simulations. Furthermore, the slopes of the spectrum follow the expected shape. Note that the IC part presents attenuations at high energies due to the Klein-Nishina suppression.

Figure 8. SSC spectrum for a power law electron distribution in the slow cooling regime. Synchrotron and IC contributions are shown (Light blue and light green dashed lines respectively). The cyan solid line represents the total flux.

Figure 11. SSC spectrum for a power law electron distribution in the fast cooling regime. Color code same as in Fig. 8

Figure 9. Injected power law electron distribution and evolution after 10 escape timescales for the slow cooling case.

Figure 12. Injected power law electron distribution and evolution after 10 escape timescales for the fast cooling case.

Figure 10. Electron interaction rates for the slow cooling case. Vertical lines represent break energies.

Figure 13. Electron interaction rates for the fast cooling case. Vertical lines represent break energies.

4 One Zone SSC Model of GRB 221009A

Following the fireball model, GRB afterglow emission is produced by the interaction of the relativistic jet and the circum-burst medium. This produces a forward shock that propagates into the medium (assumed to be uniform and cold). Our radiation zone is defined as the blast wave behind this forward shock. A reverse shock that propagates into the ejecta is also produced and as the forward shock slows down material the downstream incoming ram pressure, $\Gamma_{\text{shock}}^2 n_{\text{up}} m_p c^2$, is converted into thermal pressure, turbulent magnetic fields, outgoing ram pressure and acceleration of particles. Accelerated electrons emit synchrotron photons due to the turbulent magnetic field, which are afterwards scattered by the same electron population. For a circum-burst medium of density n_{up} , the particle density and energy density behind the shock are given by $4\Gamma n$ and $4\Gamma^2 n_{\text{up}} m_p c^2$. [2] Under the assumption that a fraction ϵ_B of the downstream energy density goes to the magnetic field we find,

$$\frac{B^2}{8\pi} = \epsilon_B 4\Gamma^2 n_{\text{up}} m_p c^2 \quad (35)$$

what leads us to the down-stream magnetic field strength

$$B = \sqrt{32\pi\epsilon_B n_{\text{up}} m_p c^2} \Gamma. \quad (36)$$

For the geometry of our blast wave we considered a shell with a width Δ located at a distance R from the star's core. The comoving volume of the shell can be estimated as

$$V = 4\pi R^2 \Delta \quad (37)$$

since the mass density of the shell is assumed to be constant we found

$$\Delta = \frac{R}{9\Gamma} \quad (38)$$

leading to a volume

$$V = \frac{4\pi R^3}{9\Gamma} \quad (39)$$

Lets now derive the dynamics of the Lorentz factor Γ . Considering that most of the energy has been transferred to the circum-burst medium, the total isotropical energy of the shock can be estimated as [2]

$$E_{\text{iso}} = \frac{4\pi\Gamma^2 R^3 n_{\text{up}} m_p c^2}{3} \quad (40)$$

Photons emitted in the shock after propagating a distance δR will be observed at a time [15]

$$\delta t \approx \frac{\delta R}{2\Gamma^2 c}. \quad (41)$$

Note that Eq. 40 implies $\Gamma^2 \propto R^{-3}$, leading to

$$t_{\text{obs}} = \frac{R}{8\Gamma^2 c} \quad (42)$$

by integrating Eq. 41. Substituting this result in Eq. 40 gives,

$$\Gamma = \left(\frac{4\pi m_p c^5 8^3}{3} \right)^{-1/8} \left(\frac{E_{\text{iso}}}{n_{\text{up}} t_{\text{obs}}^3} \right)^{1/8} \quad (43)$$

This expression allow us to estimate the gamma factor at any observation time, and hence the magnetic field.

Note that the time dependence of the shell width can be obtained from Eqs. 38 and 42

$$\Delta = \frac{8}{9} \Gamma c t_{\text{obs}} \quad (44)$$

Furthermore, we approximated the escape timescale to the dynamical timescale

$$t_{\text{esc}} \approx t_{\text{dyn}} = \frac{\Delta}{c} \quad (45)$$

Similarly, we computed the adiabatic timescale with the expansion timescale as,

$$\tau_{\text{adi}} = 3\tau_{\text{exp}} = \frac{16}{3} \Gamma t_{\text{obs}} \quad (46)$$

The synchrotron and acceleration timescale were calculated as previously presented in this text.

As before, we assume a power law energy distribution of electrons. The injected electron spectrum was normalized under the assumption that a fraction ϵ_e of the injected power is used to accelerate them,

$$\int_{E_{e,m}}^{E_{e,M}} Q_e(E_e) E_e dE_e = \epsilon_e P_{\text{in}} \quad (47)$$

where

$$P_{\text{in}} = \frac{n_{\text{up}} m_p c^3 \Gamma^2 3}{\Delta} \quad (48)$$

The maximum electron energy can be constrained utilizing Eq. 34. On the other hand, the minimum electron energy was left as a free parameter since the injection mechanism is not well understood. A value of $E_{e,m} = 25\text{GeV}$ was implemented. Moreover, we assumed that the electrons are efficiently accelerated, i.e. $\eta = 1$. With the characterizations described, we are able to construct the SSC spectrum corresponding to a specified observation time. This is performed assuming that the system converges relatively quickly to a time-dependent quasi-steady state.

Motivated by the relatively good statistics, we made a fit to the 4ks data. A redshift of $z = 0.151$ was adopted based on optical measurements [5]. The anticipated total isotropic energy is estimated to be at least 3×10^{54} erg [4]. Following [14], we have chosen to adopt a slightly higher value, $E_{\text{iso}} = 1 \times 10^{55}$ erg. In determining the density of the circum-burst medium, we opted for the density of the ISM, $n_{\text{up}} = 1\text{cm}^{-3}$. It

is noteworthy that subtle variations in these parameters do not exert a drastic influence on the resultant spectrum. Conversely, the model presents a strong dependence on ϵ_B , ϵ_e . From one side, ϵ_B correlates strongly to the location of the cooling breaks, the IC contribution, and whether we are on the slow or fast cooling regime. From the other side, the ϵ_e parameter plays a crucial role in the normalization. The model is also strongly dependent on the electron spectral index p , which was set to 2.3. ϵ_B and ϵ_e were assumed to be 8×10^{-2} and 2.5×10^{-1} respectively. Results are shown in Fig. 14.

Figure 14. Reduced SSC blast wave model spectrum. Parameters were chosen to adjust to the 4ks data. Synchrotron and IC components shown as dashed orange and blue respectively. Butterflies correspond to instrument measurements of Swift-XRT (0.3-10 keV) at 4/22 ks, MAXI (0.5-30 keV) at 2.5/8 ks, NICER (0.2-12 keV) at 14/19.5 ks, Swift-BAT (15-150 keV) at 4/22 ks, Fermi-GBM (8 keV - 40 MeV) at 0.3/0.4/1.4 ks, Fermi-LAT (20 MeV - 300 GeV) at 0.4/4/11/16 ks, GECAM-C (6 keV - 6 MeV) at 1.3-1.8 ks, and LHAASO (0.2-7TeV) at 0.5/1.3 ks approximately.

Figure 15. Time evolution of the spectrum showed in Fig. 14. Curves for observation times of 100 s, 1 ks, 4 ks and 22 ks are shown.

Using the same set of parameters, the spectrum corresponding to different observations times was computed. As appreciable in Fig. 15, our model appropriately describes the low energy data for the set of parameters decided. Additionally, we see that the curves align with the position of the breaks. Nevertheless, for this parameters, the model does not reach the TeV

data. The data could be saturated considering a higher IC component, but to do so requires a more extensive exploration of the parameter space. Moreover, interpreting the light curve reported in [4] as a transition from a coasting phase to a deceleration phase could imply the breaking down of our shock Lorentz factor relation.

5 Conclusions

GRB 221009A is a great object of study due to its remarkable brightness. Its afterglow emission appears to find potential explanation within a SSC model. We developed a time dependent SSC model employing a blast wave as our radiation zone. An analysis on the dynamics of the blast wave allowed us to parametrize physical quantities as a function of the observation time. Our model was compared to observations provided by different experiments, giving us information about the emission during a wide time span.

Despite our preliminary findings aptly describing the low-energy data, the TeV range remains way above our expectations. This discrepancy poses a significant challenge attributed to the multitude of free parameters involved and the limited observational constraints associated with them. Exploring lower values of ϵ_B could potentially yield a higher IC contribution, perhaps able to explain the TeV data. Nevertheless, this adjustment significantly impacts the low-energy part, often leading to an excess over the observed fluxes.

To fully characterize the observations with our model, a deeper exploration of the parameter space is necessary. Additionally, alternative scenarios could be investigated. For example, delving into a proton synchrotron component, induced by protons accelerated within the same zone, could offer valuable insights into this afterglow emission.

6 Acknowledgements

Coming from Honduras, a country where astroparticle physics has no presence at all, many times the desire of working in the field seemed far away. Thanks to this program, for 8 weeks, the desire that once seemed so distant became my day to day reality. Even though I hope this project to be the first of many, it will always have a place in my memories. I would like to express my huge gratitude to Walter Winter for giving me the opportunity to be part of his group during this Summer. Of course, this project wouldn't have been possible without my supervisors Chengchao Yuan and Marc Klinger. Thank you for all of the time you spent teaching me new concepts and giving me another perspective of old ones. I genuinely enjoyed your guidance. Thanks to all of the THAT group, special

thanks to Pavlo Plotko and Vasundhara Shaw for sharing a part of their story. My gratitude also to Federico Testagrossa, an amazing partner during this journey. I learned a lot with you and from you.

Thanks to the organizers of the Summer Program Gernot Maier and Sarah Seibt, for making sure that our Summer was as enjoyable as possible. Thanks to DESY for giving the opportunity to perform research at the institution and the financial support that was provided. I would like to thank the Central America and the Caribbean Astrophysics Alpha-Cen organization for the partial financial support for travel expenses and their support to my career in general. Thanks to all of the Summer Students for giving me an amazing summer outside of the academic. The experiences we shared together are extremely valuable to me, I was really lucky to be with such an incredible group.

References

- [1] E. Bissaldi, N. Omodei, M. Kerr, and Fermi-LAT Team. GRB 221009A or Swift J1913.1+1946: Fermi-LAT detection. *GRB Coordinates Network*, 32637:1, Oct. 2022.
- [2] R. D. Blandford and C. F. McKee. Fluid dynamics of relativistic blast waves. *Physics of Fluids*, 19:1130–1138, Aug. 1976.
- [3] G. R. Blumenthal and R. J. Gould. Bremsstrahlung, Synchrotron Radiation, and Compton Scattering of High-Energy Electrons Traversing Dilute Gases. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 42(2):237–271, Jan. 1970.
- [4] Z. Cao et al. A tera-electron volt afterglow from a narrow jet in an extremely bright gamma-ray burst. *Science*, 380(6652):adg9328, 2023.
- [5] A. de Ugarte Postigo, L. Izzo, G. Pugliese, D. Xu, B. Schneider, J. P. U. Fynbo, N. R. Tanvir, D. B. Malesani, A. Saccardi, D. A. Kann, K. Wiersema, B. P. Gompertz, C. C. Thoene, A. J. Levan, and Stargate Collaboration. GRB 221009A: Redshift from X-shooter/VLT. *GRB Coordinates Network*, 32648:1, Oct. 2022.
- [6] C. D. Dermer and G. Menon. *High Energy Radiation from Black Holes: Gamma Rays, Cosmic Rays, and Neutrinos*. 2009.
- [7] S. Dichiara, J. D. Gropp, J. A. Kennea, N. P. M. Kuin, A. Y. Lien, F. E. Marshall, A. Tohuvavohu, M. A. Williams, and Neil Gehrels Swift Observatory Team. Swift J1913.1+1946 a new bright hard X-ray and optical transient. *GRB Coordinates Network*, 32632:1, Oct. 2022.
- [8] H. Gao, W.-H. Lei, X.-F. Wu, and B. Zhang. Compton scattering of self-absorbed synchrotron emission. , 435(3):2520–2531, Nov. 2013.
- [9] S. Gao, M. Pohl, and W. Winter. On the direct correlation between gamma-rays and PeV neutrinos from blazars. *Astrophys. J.*, 843(2):109, 2017.
- [10] A. M. Hillas. The Origin of Ultra-High-Energy Cosmic Rays. , 22:425–444, Jan. 1984.
- [11] W. Iwakiri, G. K. Jaisawal, G. Younes, Z. Wadiasingh, S. Guillot, K. C. Gendreau, Z. Arzoumanian, E. C. Ferrara, T. Mihara, D. Pasham, J. M. Miller, A. Sanna, C. Malacaria, and C. B. Markwardt. GRB 221009A: NICER follow-up observations. *GRB Coordinates Network*, 32694:1, Oct. 2022.
- [12] M. Klinger, A. Rudolph, X. Rodrigues, C. Yuan, G. F. de Clairfontaine, A. Fedynitch, W. Winter, M. Pohl, and S. Gao. AM³: An Open-Source Tool for Time-Dependent Lepto-Hadronic Modeling of Astrophysical Sources. 12 2023.
- [13] K. Kobayashi et al. MAXI/GSC refined analysis of the bright X-ray afterglow of GRB 221009A/Swift J1913.1+1946. *The Astronomer's Telegram*, 15677:1, Oct. 2022.
- [14] S. Lesage et al. Fermi-GBM Discovery of GRB 221009A: An Extraordinarily Bright GRB from Onset to Afterglow. *Astrophys. J. Lett.*, 952(2):L42, 2023.
- [15] R. Sari. Hydrodynamics of Gamma-Ray Burst Afterglow. , 489(1):L37–L40, Nov. 1997.
- [16] R. Sari and A. A. Esin. On the Synchrotron Self-Compton Emission from Relativistic Shocks and Its Implications for Gamma-Ray Burst Afterglows. , 548(2):787–799, Feb. 2001.
- [17] R. Sari, T. Piran, and R. Narayan. Spectra and Light Curves of Gamma-Ray Burst Afterglows. , 497(1):L17–L20, Apr. 1998.
- [18] P. Veres, E. Burns, E. Bissaldi, S. Lesage, O. Roberts, and Fermi GBM Team. GRB 221009A: Fermi GBM detection of an extraordinarily bright GRB. *GRB Coordinates Network*, 32636:1, Oct. 2022.
- [19] B. Zhang. *The Physics of Gamma-Ray Bursts*. 2018.